

AI·EFFECT

Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility
For the Energy sector

D2.1 AI-EFFECT Architecture Design

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Executive Summary

In this report, we propose a modular architecture for the AI-EFFECT TEF. The TEF will provide uniform access for AI vendors to test and experimentation capabilities offered by a collection of nodes, e.g., universities, institutes, or companies. Each node may itself contain multiple stakeholders, e.g., the node owner, the test facility management, and data handlers/providers. Each test or experimentation capability offered by the node is implemented as a *workflow*, typically at the AI on Demand platform. Each workflow is composed of a set of standardized *services*, e.g., data provision or neural network training, which may be reused across different workflows developed by different nodes. In the report, we discuss different configurations regarding where the tests are performed, e.g., locally at the vendor's premises or locally at the node, depending on the sensitivity of the involved data or AI solutions, and we describe relevant technologies for facilitating the sharing of such sensitive information. Furthermore, we describe how to implement the architecture in a secure way to protect all involved data from unauthorized access. We also describe specific considerations related to workflows involving physical test and experimentation facilities as well as workflows involving multiple nodes. Finally, we describe a number of technologies that are relevant to facilitating the communication of data and AI solutions in a standardized way, e.g., functional mock-up units and VILLASnode.

1 Introduction and objectives

There exist many AI vendors that develop solutions for solving problems in the energy sector, e.g., optimal charging of electrical vehicles, minimizing supply temperatures in district heating grids, and shifting energy consumption to times with high renewable energy penetration. However, AI solutions are typically based on some mathematical representation of reality with a certain set of assumptions. Consequently, a poorly developed model is likely to result in poor performance and adverse behavior. Therefore, it is imperative to test the solutions before they are commissioned. Furthermore, early and continuous testing and experimentation can significantly improve the efficiency of the design process for AI vendors. Finally, if an AI solution has successfully completed a set of well-defined tests and validations, the vendor can document the capabilities of their solution to potential customers.

However, the test facilities that are relevant to AI vendors are spread out over Europe, and some solutions may even require several different test facilities. Consequently, it is not straightforward for vendors to test and experiment with their solutions. Therefore, the objective of the AI-EFFECT project is to 1) provide a common entry point AI vendors targeting the energy sector to identify test and experimentation facilities (TEFs) and 2) facilitate the interconnection between the two parties, as illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2. This is referred to as the AI-EFFECT TEF.

Figure 1 The objective of the AI-EFFECT TEF is to interconnect AI vendors and test and experimentation facilities (TEFs).

Objectives. The main objective of this report is to describe an architecture for interconnecting AI vendors with relevant ‘nodes’ containing one or more TEFs and potentially interconnecting with potential ‘satellite’ facilities, i.e., a node doesn’t have to be a single geographical location such as a university or technical institute. Additionally, the architecture should address the following subobjectives.

- **Modularity:** The architecture should permit the addition of new nodes and satellites without affecting those that are already part of the AI-EFFECT TEF.
- **Intranodal architecture:** The architecture describes how to connect tools and satellites within a single node.
- **Internodal architecture:** The architecture also describes how to perform tests and experiments involving multiple nodes, e.g., for testing AI solutions that span multiple sectors.
- The architecture should utilize a trust model framework and facilitate security by design through zero-trust and zero-touch deployment and configuration methods. This includes least-privilege policies with access control policies that restrict the access to sensitive data and AI solutions.

In addition to describing the proposed architecture, the objectives of this document are to

- Describe specific technologies (e.g., encryption and functional mock-up units) for implementing the architecture in practice.
- Analyze the technical requirements of the proposed architecture based on the technologies.

Outline. The remainder of this report is structured as follows. In Section 2, we describe the relevant details of the AI solutions that may be tested by the AI-EFFECT platform as well as the test and experimentation facilities and organization of the Danish node. Next, in Section 3, we discuss various technologies, e.g., encryption, that are relevant to sharing either data or AI solutions confidentially between the vendor and the node and test facilities. In Section 4, we discuss how these technologies extend to the interconnection of multiple nodes, and in Section 5, we present a detailed discussion and analysis of the technical requirements necessary to use and implement the technologies in the AI-EFFECT framework. Finally, in Section 6, we discuss how the content of this report is relevant to other tasks and work packages in the AI-EFFECT project, and in Section 7, we present conclusions.

Figure 2 AI-EFFECT framework.

2 Background

In this section, we present background information that is relevant to the architecture proposed in Section 3. The architecture will rely heavily on the AI-on-Demand platform described in Section 2.1, and the objective is to interconnect nodes which facilitate the connection to test facilities as described in Section 2.2. In Section 2.3, we discuss different types of AI solutions and how it affects the way that they are tested, and in Section 2.4, we discuss a variety of security aspects that are relevant to sharing data and AI solutions within the AI-EFFECT TEF.

2.1 AI-on-Demand platform (AI4EU)

The European AI-on-Demand platform¹ (AIoD) was developed through the EU funded projects AI4Europe (sometimes AI4EU) and DeployAI. The objective of the platform is to accelerate innovation in AI while maintaining a focus on trust, transparency, and accountability, and the platform is intended to serve as a one-stop hub for AI. For the research and innovation community, the platform offers datasets, tools, and software relevant to developing and testing AI solutions, and for industry (incl. SMEs, startups, and the public sector), it offers mature AI solutions, support for implementation/deployment, European hosting environments, and an AI marketplace, which can facilitate the development, training, and deployment of the utilization of the solutions.

More specifically, the platform offers a visual designer for creating *workflows* consisting of *services* that constitute, e.g., an AI solution or a testing sequence for such a solution. The user uses ‘protobuf’ definitions (see Section 5.4) to specify the types of the inputs and outputs of each individual service, e.g., a numerical value or a text string, in order to ensure the interoperability of the services that are combined into workflows. Once the workflow has been designed, it can either be executed directly on the AIoD platform or it can be deployed at local premises, e.g., if the workflow involves physical test facilities or has a high computational demand in terms of computing power or memory.

¹ <https://aiod.eu>

Figure 3 Overview of the Danish node. The 'TEF Platform' refers to the AI-EFFECT TEF.

2.2 Nodes

In this report, a *node* refers to an entity, e.g., a university or a research institute, that facilitates the access to experimental facilities. Typically, the node will have its own facilities, either classical physical test environments or digital environments (software and mathematical algorithms) that carry out the test. Additionally, the nodes may be connected with satellite facilities, e.g., a research institute with specific test facilities that are relevant to the tests offered by the node. Finally, the node may also include the connection to *data providers*, i.e., entities such as companies or research labs that provide data without offering test facilities.

2.2.1 Example: The Danish node

The objective of the Danish node is to enable the test, experimentation, and analysis of AI solutions for district heating systems and sector coupling with, e.g., power systems – for instance, through electric boilers and heat pumps. The node contains several partners, including two departments at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU): Department of Wind and Energy Systems (DTU Wind) and Department of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science (DTU Compute), the digital infrastructure company Center Denmark (CDK), and the utility company Bornholms Energy og Forsyning (BEOF). CDK provides access to data provided by the utility company TREFOR. The node contains four types of test and experimentation facilities:

1. State of the art methods for assessing the interpretability and verifying (in terms of mathematical guarantees) the constraint satisfaction of AI solutions.
2. The lab facilities at Energy System Integration Lab (SYSLAB) at DTU Wind², which provides a controlled test environment for, among other things, testing solutions for control and optimization of district heating systems.
3. The living lab test data on heat demands and consumer-side forward and return temperatures from smart meters provided by CDK on behalf of TREFOR. This data is also enriched with local weather forecasts.
4. Operational data on heat demands in the district heating grid operated (and provided) by BEOF.

Figure 3 illustrates the interconnection and roles of the partners. DTU Wind, DTU Compute, and BEOF will develop AI solutions that can be used to test the AI-EFFECT platform itself, i.e., is it possible to submit an AI solution and receive the test results (node-centric) or to download a test routine and test the AI solution

² wind.dtu.dk/facilities/powerlabdk-facilities/syslab.

yourself (vendor-centric)? The data shared by TREFOR is handled by CDK, and the data shared by BEOF is handled by Energydata.dk³ which is a platform developed by PowerLab⁴ at DTU Wind. Furthermore, data is also exchanged between CDK and Energydata.dk.

2.2.2 Stakeholders in a node

As exemplified by the Danish node described in Section 2.2.1, a node may involve multiple stakeholders. The main types of stakeholders are

1. The node owner.
2. The test facility management.
3. Data handlers.
4. Data providers.

A given organization, e.g., a university or department, may represent multiple types of stakeholders. For instance, in the Danish node, the department DTU Wind is both the node owner and the manager of the test facilities. However, it may still be different entities within the department, and in general, complex node constellations will also require orchestration. In the following, we comment on the nature and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in a node.

Node owner. The node owner is responsible for coordinating the interaction between the different stakeholders in the node. They may either directly lead the effort to design test and experimentation workflows or provide overall instructions to be followed when the individual stakeholders design their workflows.

Test facility management. Test facilities are typically physical and involve testing equipment used in the designed workflows, but they may also include virtual test facilities where, e.g., high-fidelity mathematical models are used to assess the quality of AI solutions. The facility management is responsible for carrying out the experiments for assessing the efficacy of the AI solutions. This may involve experimental planning (customization) before the experiment, communication and consulting during the experiment, and interpretation of results after the experiment. All of these activities may also involve the AI vendor, and the communication may either be direct (e.g., physical or online meetings) or through automatic systems (digital forms filled out by the vendor).

Data handlers. A data handler is responsible for the communication of data between the other stakeholders (data providers, node owner, and test facility) without providing data itself. The Danish node involves two data handlers: Energy.data.dk and CDK. Typically, the data handlers will also have capabilities for processing (e.g., anonymization/pseudonymization) and visualization of data, facilitate access to data spaces, and merging with other data sets (e.g., public weather forecasts). The data handler may also provide the link to data providers which are not directly associated with the node, as is the case in the Danish node where CDK provides data from TREFOR.

Data providers. The data providers provide data that is relevant to carrying out the experiments with the AI solutions. In some cases, the AI solution will directly process the data and be assessed on the result and in others, the data is used by the test facility to design a meaningful experiment. Again, the Danish node contains two data providers: BEOF and TREFOR.

2.3 Types of AI solutions

The technical requirements for sharing, testing, and experimentation of AI solutions will depend on the nature of the solution and the data it uses. Figure 4 illustrates key aspects in terms of how the results of the AI solution are used and what type of data it uses. Some AI solutions passively analyze data from a process or real system and provide a human user (e.g., a process operator) with the results or suggestions for actions (top left). Other solutions autonomously (or semi-autonomously) analyze data, determine

³ energydata.dk.

⁴ powerlab.dk.

Figure 4 AI solutions may either require 1) one-way communication (top left) because the results are returned to a human user or 2) two-way communication (bottom left) because the results are returned to the processes itself. Similarly, AI solutions may be used to process 1) a batch of data in a one-off analysis (top right) or 2) a real-time signal where the AI solution performs an analysis or makes a decision every time new measurements become available (bottom right).

appropriate actions, and implement those actions (bottom left). In either case, the analysis and actions may be based on a batch of data that is processed one time (top right) or on a stream of data that is processed one data point at the time (bottom right).

In general, there are fewer challenges associated with testing AI solutions that provide a human user with the result of an analysis because the real system is unaffected by the analysis, i.e., the AI solution cannot cause problems to the real system. In contrast, a solution whose proposed actions must be tested on the real system requires guarantees that there will not be adverse effects. Similarly, using an AI solution to analyze a batch of data offline has fewer real-time processing constraints than an online analysis of data that is streamed in real-time.

2.4 Security aspects and trust models

As some test and experimentation activities involve data from real customers/consumers which may be protected by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), it cannot be shared with third parties, e.g., AI vendors, without a legal data sharing agreement. Creating such agreements can both be time-consuming, laborious, and in some cases, not possible. Similarly, AI vendors will have a natural incentive to protect their AI solutions as intellectual property (IP). Consequently, there is a need to explore technical solutions that can enable the sharing of data and AI solutions without violating GDPR or compromising IP rights. It is not straightforward to process data or encrypt AI solutions such that they can be shared.

Trust between a data provider (data owner) and an AI model vendor can be formalised using two guiding questions that define the underlying trust assumptions of the collaboration.

QP: Is the processing party trusted to follow the agreed protocol and produce a correct result?

QC: Is the processing party trusted to ensure confidentiality and privacy of the data throughout processing?

The combination of answers to these two questions determines the applicable trust model and, consequently, the level and type of security controls required.

Full Trust Model. When both QP (trust in correct protocol execution and correctness of results) and QC (trust in confidentiality and privacy protection) are answered positively, the collaboration follows a Full Trust Model. In this setting, the data provider, the AI model vendor, and the party operating the execution

environment are assumed to act as intended and to apply appropriate organisational and technical safeguards. The security architecture can therefore rely primarily on established best practices—identity and access management, encrypted communications and storage, controlled operational access, and audit logging—to mitigate accidental disclosure and to support traceability, while correctness is mainly ensured through standard validation and reproducibility procedures.

Semi-Trusted Model. When QP is positive, but QC is negative, the collaboration corresponds to an Honest-but-Curious (Semi-Trusted) Model. Under this model, the processing party is assumed to follow the agreed workflow and produce correct outputs but is not trusted to refrain from attempting to infer sensitive information from the inputs, intermediate states, or detailed outputs. Consequently, the security requirements must extend beyond perimeter and access controls and include technical mechanisms that enforce confidentiality by design. This typically implies restricting visibility of plaintext data and sensitive model artefacts through privacy-preserving execution (e.g., execution within a trusted execution environment or computation on encrypted data – see Sections 4.4 and 4.5 for more information), combined with output minimisation policies that limit results to agreed KPIs and prevent leakage through high-granularity traces, intermediate representations, or debugging artefacts.

Malicious Model. When both QP and QC are negative, the collaboration must be analysed under an Untrusted (Malicious) Model. In this case, the processing party may deviate from the protocol in order to manipulate results, bias KPIs, or selectively omit steps, while also attempting to compromise confidentiality through exfiltration, side channels, or deliberate misuse of operational privileges. Supporting collaboration under this model requires a stronger assurance framework that reduces reliance on behavioural trust assumptions. From an architectural perspective, this implies combining confidentiality-preserving computation with mechanisms that strengthen integrity and accountability, such as attestation-gated execution in tightly controlled environments, tamper-evident provenance of artefacts and configurations, and auditable evidence linking reported results to a specific model version, dataset version, and execution context.

Impact of the considered trust model. The selected trust model has a direct and significant impact on which Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) are appropriate and feasible in AI-EFFECT, because each trust assumption determines what must be protected against and what can be assumed about the behaviour of the processing party. In a fully trusted setting, where the processor is assumed to both preserve confidentiality and execute the protocol correctly, privacy requirements can often be satisfied through secure data sharing and fine-grained access control, without requiring heavy cryptographic protection during computation. In an honest-but-curious setting, where correct execution is expected but confidentiality cannot be assumed, the architecture must adopt secure/private computation techniques that minimise or eliminate exposure of plaintext to the processing party, such as homomorphic encryption, multi-party computation, functional encryption, or controlled perturbation approaches. In an untrusted setting, where neither confidentiality nor correct execution can be assumed, PET selection shifts toward stronger mechanisms that reduce reliance on operator honesty and constrain the execution environment, such as trusted execution environments combined with strict control of data processing and, where applicable, MPC-based protocols (see Section 4.4). As a result, PET selection cannot be treated as a purely technical preference; it must be derived from the trust model of the collaboration, since this determines the required assurance level, the acceptable overhead, and the overall design of the computation workflow.

3 Architecture

In this section, we describe a modular architecture for the AI-EFFECT TEF based on the requirements described in Section 1. The first parts of this section focus on the case where the testing and experimentation only involves a single node. In Section 3.6, we describe special considerations for internodal testing, i.e., workflows involving multiple nodes. The user of the TEF will typically start their testing campaign by browsing through test functionality and facilities at the AI-EFFECT platform

Figure 5 Overview of the elements in the architecture described in Section 3. The platform and the workflow layer are also described in Section 3 together with the security layer, and in Section 4 and 5, we describe relevant technologies shown in this chart for the security layer and the infrastructural layer, respectively.

described in Section 3.1. Ultimately, the tests will consist of services and workflows that are typically implemented through the AIoD portal (see Section 2.1), as described in Section 3.2, which may be designed in a node- or vendor-centric manner, as described in Section 3.3. Furthermore, the AI-EFFECT TEF platform will feature a high level of infrastructural security measures, as described in Section 3.4 (see also Section 2.4), including guidelines for designing workflows where data and/or AI solutions cannot be shared freely. Figure 5 shows an overview of the elements and layers in the AI-EFFECT TEF: The workflow layer where individual services (e.g., data provision) are combined to create test and experimentation workflows, the infrastructural layer where building blocks (e.g., simulators and functional mockup units (FMUs)) are combined into services, and the security layer that handles the sharing of sensitive information such as data, AI solutions, or both.

This report has been written concurrently with the D1.2 deliverable report on the operating principles of the AI-EFFECT TEF, and the two documents complement each other but also both discuss subjects such as confidentiality and data security and modularity of the platform.

3.1 AI-EFFECT platform

The AI-EFFECT platform will offer a single-entry point for users of the AI-EFFECT TEF. Typically, the users of the platform will be AI vendors, and they will use it to browse through the services and workflows offered by the nodes connected to the TEF.

Business use cases. The platform will feature a number of business use cases that describe a key problem faced by specific types of companies. For instance, a district heating system operator may spend excessive amounts of energy on heating the water in their distribution grid because they are unable to accurately predict/forecast the future heat demands of their customers. The description will list the key performance indicators relevant to the use case, e.g., cost of operation, as well as operational constraints and thresholds.

AI solution interfaces. To ensure interoperability, the AI solution developed by the vendor must conform to a specific interface, i.e., the specific services or workflows expects a software implementation of the AI solution with certain input arguments, e.g., historical heat demands and a prediction/forecasting horizon, and outputs, e.g., forecasts of future heat demands over the specified horizon. The vendor will query the interface from the platform, which passes the query on to the node providing the service or workflow. The

Figure 6 Example of a workflow consisting of the four services 'Data provision', 'Aggregation', 'Train neural network', and 'Test forecast accuracy'. This workflow could, for instance, test a neural network for forecasting future aggregate heat demands of consumers in a district heating grid. The data provision service would access the raw data from the data provider (e.g., the company Center Denmark) and pass it on to the aggregation service, which processes the data in order to reduce its dimensionality (see Section 5.2). Next, the neural network is trained on the aggregated data and tested, e.g., by forecasting historical data that was not used in the training.

node returns the interface to the platform, which passes it to the AI vendor that can create a wrapper or software implementation of their solution that conforms to the interface, e.g., using docker containers and functional mockup units. Once the implementation conforms to the interface, it can be tested either at the vendor's premise or at the node (see Section 3.3).

Test results. The platform will visualize the results of the specific test. For some AI solutions (see Section 2.3), the results will only be visualized once the entire test has been completed, e.g., solutions that process a batch of data. For solutions that involve continuous processing of data, the platform may also provide the opportunity of monitoring the progress of the test, e.g., to allow the user to conclude the test early if the key performance indicators are too low or constraints are violated.

3.2 Workflows and services

The nodes associated with the AI-EFFECT TEF will decompose their test and experimentation procedures into workflows consisting of individual services. The purpose is that many services, e.g., data provision, will be relevant to many different types of nodes and testing workflows (see the D1.1 report⁵ for a list of services). The services are designed and implemented during the development of the AI-EFFECT TEF, and the node owners will create workflows by combining services in the AIoD platform. In certain cases, a node owner may wish to customize their workflow and thus not use the AIoD platform. In such a case, it is the owner's responsibility to ensure interoperability with the AI-EFFECT platform. Figure 6 shows an example of a workflow consisting of four services. If necessary, the node owners may add custom services and incorporate them into their workflows. In order to facilitate the discovery of existing services, an AI Catalogue will be developed, as described in the D3.1 report⁶. It recommends enriching the services with metadata, e.g., description, category (data, model), and domain (power transmission, congestion management, district heating). Note that a workflow may involve multiple stakeholders (node owner, test facilities, data handlers/providers) as described in Section 2.2.2. Regardless of where the workflow is executed (AIoD, cloud, locally at the node, or locally at the vendor's premises), the workflow may require communication and exchange of data with one or more stakeholders. This is referred to as *orchestration*, and in Task 3.1 of WP3, an orchestrator will be developed for handling the coordination of communicating data and executing services offered by different stakeholders.

3.3 Node-centric vs. vendor-centric workflows

The AI-EFFECT platform will facilitate automatic interconnection of AI vendors that develop solutions for the energy sector and facilities for test and experimentation that are relevant to AI solutions. The nodes' testing workflows may either be designed in a node-centric or vendor-centric manner:

1. Node-centric: 1) The AI vendor queries/requests an interface specification from the AI-EFFECT platform and designs/implements their solution according to this specification. 2) The vendor submits their solution to the platform which passes it onto the node. The node carries out the requested tests and returns the results to the platform which passes it onto the AI vendor, e.g.,

⁵ <https://ai-effect.eu/d1-1-design-of-ai-effect-use-cases-and-outputs>

⁶ <https://ai-effect.eu/d3-1-ai-services-onboarding-and-ai-effect-catalogue>

with a graphical presentation of the key performance indicators (KPIs) and the conclusion of the test.

2. Vendor-centric: The AI vendor queries/requests a test routine or software that can be executed on the vendor's premises. The software would include the data that is relevant for the test.

Although the term 'node-centric' suggests that workflows are executed locally at the node (which is an option), it is also possible that the workflow is executed directly in the AIoD platform or that the node utilizes another cloud-based solution for executing parts or all of the workflow. Figure 7 shows an example of communication in a node-centric workflow. If both data and AI solutions can be shared freely, the choice between the two depends solely on the nature of the test. For instance, mathematical analyses of interpretability and verification of constraint satisfaction of a given AI solution may be carried out either at the node or the vendor's premises. However, a physical lab test can, of course, not be carried out solely on the vendor's side. Furthermore, there are often constraints on how freely data and AI solutions can be shared. In Section 3.4.4, we discuss the technological possibilities for enabling the sharing of data and solutions in order to enable the implementation of both node-centric and vendor-centric workflows.

3.4 Security aspects

In this section, we discuss aspects of sharing data and AI solutions within the AI-EFFECT TEF and the nodes in it.

3.4.1 Scope, assets, and security objectives

Security in AI-EFFECT covers (i) data exchanged and processed during experimentation, (ii) AI solutions and associated artefacts provided by vendors, (iii) platform and node infrastructure used to execute workflows, and (iv) interfaces to physical or simulated test facilities. The security requirements must support both node-centric and vendor-centric designs.

In a node-centric (data owner) design, the AI vendor delivers the solution to the AI-EFFECT platform and the workload is executed on an AI-EFFECT node under node/operator control. This design improves comparability and transparency of benchmarking because execution conditions can be standardised and centrally observed; however, it concentrates confidentiality and integrity risks at the node because the node executes vendor-provided artefacts against potentially sensitive datasets. Consequently, node-centric security requirements must ensure that the data owner's datasets cannot be exfiltrated or inferred by the submitted solution beyond the authorised outputs, and that the vendor's intellectual property (model weights, binaries, containers, pre/post-processing logic) is not exposed to node operators or other tenants. This implies strong workload isolation, strict access control and least privilege, controlled and auditable data access, restriction of network egress and output channels, and integrity-protected experiment configurations and logs. Where data and/or models cannot be shared in plaintext, node-centric security must additionally rely on Computation Nodes implementing privacy-preserving execution (e.g., TEE/SGX with attestation-gated secret release, or HE-based processing on encrypted data) so that collaboration remains possible without disclosing protected assets.

In a vendor-centric design, the vendor controls the execution environment and executes the test routine and/or evaluation pipeline at the vendor premises. This reduces exposure of vendor IP to external operators but shifts the primary security concerns toward protecting the confidentiality of test datasets provided to the vendor and ensuring the credibility and integrity of benchmarking outcomes when execution is not under platform control. Vendor-centric security requirements must therefore define how datasets can be shared safely (e.g., via minimisation, anonymisation/pseudonymisation, aggregation, or synthetic data), or alternatively how encrypted datasets can be used when sharing is otherwise not permissible. In addition, vendor-centric security must provide integrity and accountability mechanisms that allow stakeholders to trust reported results, including signed and versioned test routines and configurations, traceable provenance of artefacts, and auditable evidence linking KPIs to a specific dataset and execution configuration. Overall, supporting both designs requires that the architecture expresses security objectives and controls independently of where execution occurs, and that it selects the

appropriate execution pattern—node-centric, vendor-centric, or Computation Node-based—according to the shareability constraints of the data and the AI solution.

Taken together, stating that “security requirements must support both node-centric and vendor-centric designs” means that the Security section should not assume a single execution placement. Instead, it should define security objectives and controls that remain applicable when execution moves between node and vendor premises, and it should explicitly connect those controls to the document’s “shareability” constraints (data shareable or not, AI solution shareable or not, and whether physical facilities are involved) that determine where tests can be executed in the first place.

Primary security objectives. Privacy and confidentiality requirements address different, complementary protection goals for the AI-EFFECT data lake and the sensitive datasets it hosts. Privacy requirements focus on protecting people (or data subjects) by preventing sensitive information from being linked back to an identifiable individual. In the context illustrated, this means avoiding or strictly controlling the association between sensitive records and identity—through measures such as minimisation of personal identifiers, pseudonymisation/anonymisation, aggregation to reduce granularity, and governance controls aligned with regulatory frameworks (e.g., GDPR). The central question for privacy is therefore whether processing, storage, or outputs could enable re-identification or inference about individuals beyond the permitted purpose.

By contrast, confidentiality requirements focus on protecting the data as a valuable asset, regardless of whether it is personal, by preventing unauthorised access, disclosure, or leakage of sensitive datasets and derived artefacts. In the slide’s terms, confidentiality is about securing the data lake and the “valuable assets to be protected” via access control, encryption in transit and at rest, key management, segregation between tenants/experiments, and secure execution environments when processing cannot be fully trusted. The central question for confidentiality is whether any unauthorised party—external attackers, insiders, or other tenants—could gain access to the sensitive data or model artefacts.

To summarize, we list below the list of security requirements that need to be considered in AI-Effect.

- **Confidentiality:** prevent unauthorised disclosure of datasets, metadata, models, parameters, and intermediate artefacts.
- **Privacy:** prevent the identification or re-identification of individuals and prevent unauthorised inference of personal or sensitive attributes from datasets, metadata, model outputs, or intermediate artefacts.
- **Integrity:** prevent tampering datasets, experiment configurations, software artefacts, and reported KPIs.
- **Availability:** ensure services remain reliably accessible and resilient to failures and abuse.
- **Accountability:** provide auditability for actions, access, and workflow execution, supporting repeatable benchmarking and investigation.

3.4.2 Information Security

3.4.2.1 Assets and classification

Data owner assets. It include the raw datasets provided for experimentation as well as the accompanying metadata that can increase sensitivity, such as timestamps, identifiers, topology or location references, and operational annotations. They also include derived features and intermediate representations, because these can still preserve behavioural patterns (e.g., load profiles) that enable re-identification or inference of sensitive operational states. Finally, experiment outputs must be considered part of the protected asset set when returned at high granularity, since predictions, traces, or anomaly flags can leak information about individuals or critical infrastructure operations, including in GDPR-relevant settings.

Model owner assets. They cover the full bundle of artefacts that represent vendor intellectual property and enable execution or reproduction of the solution. This includes containers and binaries, model weights and parameters, and the architectural design of the model. It also includes proprietary pre- and post-processing logic and configuration, since these elements often encode domain know-how and performance tuning and may enable reverse engineering when exposed.

Platform artefacts. They include the experiment definitions that specify what was tested and how, the logs and execution traces produced during runs, and the KPI reports and benchmarking results delivered to stakeholders. These artefacts are security-relevant because they underpin trust and repeatability; they must be integrity-protected and auditable, and linked through provenance information to the exact dataset, model artefacts, and configuration used to generate results.

3.4.2.2 *Data lifecycle controls.*

The platform shall support controls for each stage:

Ingestion & preparation. The platform should enforce purpose-based data minimisation (only fields required for the experiment are ingested) and perform schema/format validation (e.g., expected time resolution, units, missing values, identifier fields) to reduce accidental inclusion of unnecessary sensitive attributes. Where sharing is constrained, the platform should support optional privacy-oriented preparation such as anonymisation and synthetic data generation when it enables lawful/contractual sharing while preserving benchmarking utility.

Storage. All persisted datasets and artefacts (including intermediate results and backups) should be protected with encryption at rest, and access should be governed by least privilege with clear separation between experiments and tenants. The platform should require explicit retention and deletion rules per dataset/experiment (aligned with purpose limitation and agreements), including deletion of temporary artefacts after runs and controlled retention of only the necessary KPI outputs and provenance records.

Processing. The platform should enforce that sensitive datasets are executed only in approved environments consistent with the dataset's "shareability" constraints, by embedding these constraints into scheduling and workflow policies. In practice, this means dispatching runs to standard nodes only when data/model can be handled within baseline controls, and routing runs to Computation Nodes when data and/or model cannot be shared, requiring TEE/SGX or HE execution modes; a run that requires a given mode should be blocked from execution on non-compliant infrastructure.

Output handling. Outputs should be restricted to the agreed KPIs and authorised result formats defined by the experiment, with explicit prevention of uncontrolled extraction of sensitive intermediates. Where leakage risk exists, the platform should support output filtering or aggregation (e.g., return summary statistics rather than high-resolution traces) and limit access to debug artefacts (e.g., feature dumps, intermediate representations, gradients) unless explicitly approved and justified for the experiment.

3.4.2.3 *Confidential collaboration through Computation Nodes*

AI-EFFECT should provide Computation Nodes as a dedicated execution environment that enables collaboration when either the dataset, the AI solution, or both cannot be shared in a conventional way. The platform orchestrates the workflow and records provenance, while the Computation Node enforces a defined trust boundary so that only authorised outputs (e.g., KPIs) leave the execution context and neither party is required to disclose protected assets to the other or to infrastructure operators beyond what is strictly necessary for the experiment.

TEE-based Computation Node (SGX). In this mode, confidentiality is achieved by executing the model and processing plaintext data inside an SGX enclave. The enclave boundary is treated as the only location where sensitive data and model logic may exist in plaintext, while all external components (host OS, hypervisor, administrators) are considered untrusted. Remote attestation is integrated as a mandatory gating step: the data owner and/or model owner verifies enclave identity and configuration (i.e., that the expected enclave build and policy are running) before releasing secrets such as data decryption keys, model weights, or other runtime credentials into the enclave. Results are produced within the enclave and re-encrypted before leaving it, and the workflow should restrict output granularity to prevent leakage through intermediate artefacts unless explicitly authorised.

A TEE-based Computation Node can provide strong confidentiality for both the model and the data during processing, because the model code (including architecture implementation details), associated configuration, and model parameters can be loaded and executed inside the enclave, while the host OS/hypervisor and node operators are treated as untrusted. In this trust model, the vendor's IP (model binaries/containers, architecture logic, parameter values) and the data owner's plaintext inputs are

intended to be visible only within the enclave boundary, with remote attestation used to gate the release of secrets. In deliverable terms, SGX offers confidentiality “by construction” at runtime against privileged infrastructure access, while acknowledging that this is not an absolute guarantee against all classes of attacks (e.g., certain side-channel threats), which must be managed through hardening and operational policy.

HE-based Computation Node. In this mode, confidentiality for the data owner is achieved by ensuring the Computation Node operates on ciphertexts only. The data owner (or an authorised client under the data owner’s control) encrypts inputs and retains the secret key, while the node receives only encrypted datasets together with the necessary public/evaluation keys to enable computation. The platform should enforce that secret keys are never uploaded to or stored by the node/platform, and that encrypted artefacts are transferred and persisted under secure transport and encrypted storage with strict access control. The Computation Node returns encrypted outputs that can be decrypted only by the data owner/client, and the platform maintains integrity and traceability through versioning and provenance so that results can be linked to the exact model artefacts and experiment configuration used, even though the node cannot interpret the plaintext data it processes.

An HE-based Computation Node primarily provides confidentiality for the data owner’s inputs during processing by ensuring the computing node operates on ciphertexts, with the secret key retained by the data owner/client. However, HE does not automatically provide confidentiality for the model structure. In typical HE/FHE workflows, the model must be expressed as an HE-compatible computation graph (or circuit) using a specific library’s supported operations and encodings; as a result, the computing node generally learns the model’s functional form (e.g., layer types, ordering, and sometimes approximation choices such as polynomial activations), even if certain elements such as parameter values can be protected depending on how the workflow is implemented. Practically, this means that HE can enforce strong input-data confidentiality without trusting the node, but model confidentiality is limited unless additional measures are used (e.g., vendor-side execution, TEE+HE hybrid, or other privacy-preserving protocols), and this trade-off should be made explicit in the architecture.

Computation node location. AI-EFFECT should explicitly support three valid deployment placements for the Computation Node—within the AI Vendor domain, within the Data Owner domain, or within a separate cloud-based domain—because the location materially changes the trust assumptions, the attack surface, and the operational controls required. When the Computation Node is hosted inside the AI Vendor domain, infrastructure governance (networking, IAM, patching, monitoring) is naturally strongest for the vendor, and model confidentiality is easier to maintain because the vendor can keep the full model toolchain and artefacts under its own administrative control; however, the Data Owner must rely more heavily on technical guarantees (e.g., TEE remote attestation or HE) and strict output governance to ensure dataset confidentiality and to prevent data exposure to vendor administrators or tooling. When the Computation Node is hosted inside the Data Owner domain, the Data Owner gains stronger operational assurance around data residency, logging, and access controls, and can reduce the risk of dataset exposure to third parties; however, the AI Vendor’s IP protection becomes more dependent on cryptographic enforcement (e.g., enclave execution with attested key release, or packaging/signing with strict runtime policy) because the model artefacts now execute on infrastructure administered by another party. When the Computation Node is hosted in a separate cloud-based domain (neutral environment), neither party is structurally advantaged by administrative control, so the design must assume the cloud operator and platform operators are untrusted by default and must therefore lean on “verifiable compute” patterns such as TEE-based confidential computing with mandatory attestation-gated key release and/or HE-based ciphertext-only processing; this setting typically provides the cleanest separation of duties and most balanced governance, but it also introduces additional requirements for connectivity (private links), identity federation, dual-party policy enforcement, and rigorous provenance/audit to ensure both parties can independently verify what ran and what left the execution boundary.

3.4.2.4 Cryptographic protections and key management.

Encryption in transit (node ↔ platform ↔ vendor). For service-to-service mutual authentication and encrypted channels, a practical implementation is to use SPIFFE/SPIRE⁷ to issue short-lived workload identities (X.509 SVIDs) and rotate certificates automatically, combined with a service mesh such as Istio to enforce mutual TLS between workloads by default and progressively “lock down” namespaces/meshes to mTLS-only traffic.

Encryption at rest (datasets and model artefacts). For node and platform storage encryption on Linux, a widely used baseline is dm-crypt with LUKS (managed via cryptsetup⁸) to encrypt block devices/volumes that host datasets, artefact stores, and backups. This provides OS-level encryption at rest and is well documented for operational hardening and lifecycle procedures (setup, key slots, rotation practices, recovery).

Key management policy (ownership, rotation, revocation, separation of duties, access logging). For centralised key lifecycle management with strong auditability, a common solution is HashiCorp Vault⁹. Vault’s Transit secrets engine provides “cryptography as a service” for encryption/signing/HMAC without storing the application data, and Vault also provides a Key Management secrets engine for consistent lifecycle management and integration patterns. These components map directly to requirements such as controlled key custody, rotation and revocation workflows, and access logging/auditing of cryptographic operations.

HE-specific constraint. When the workflow uses Homomorphic Encryption, the policy should explicitly enforce that the secret key remains with the data owner/client. In practice this is supported by common HE libraries (e.g., Microsoft SEAL¹⁰) where encrypted computation results remain decryptable only with the secret key held by the data owner, and by widely used FHE libraries such as OpenFHE¹¹ which implement standard schemes for ciphertext-only computation.

3.4.3 Platform and infrastructure Security

As illustrated in Figure 6, the platform is organized around three cooperating domains: the Data Owner environment, the AI Vendor node¹², and a neutral Computation Node where processing occurs inside a protected execution boundary. Although depicted as a separate domain for clarity and separation of duties, the Computation Node is a logically isolated execution environment and may be deployed either within a neutral cloud tenancy or physically and administratively hosted inside the AI Vendor or the Data Owner domain. The choice of placement does not alter the fundamental security model—sensitive data and model artefacts remain protected by cryptographic and hardware-enforced boundaries—but it does change the operational trust assumptions and control responsibilities.

The platform and nodes shall implement a baseline security posture:

Identity and Access Management (IAM): The platform and nodes shall implement a coherent IAM model that governs both human and machine identities and that can be applied consistently across distributed deployments. Role-based access control shall be used to express what actions a given actor is allowed to perform, distinguishing clearly between roles such as platform administrators, node operators, data owners, and AI vendors. Permissions shall follow the principle of least privilege, meaning that users and services are granted only the minimum rights required to execute their tasks and only for the minimum duration necessary. In addition, segregation of duties shall be enforced to reduce the risk of abuse or accidental misuse, for example by separating responsibilities for infrastructure administration,

⁷ SPIFFE Project. (n.d.). Working with SVIDs. SPIFFE Documentation.

⁸ Linux Kernel Documentation. (n.d.). dm-crypt. Linux Kernel Documentation (device-mapper).

⁹ HashiCorp. (n.d.). Transit secrets engine. HashiCorp Vault Documentation.

¹⁰ Microsoft. (n.d.). Microsoft SEAL. GitHub Repository Documentation.

¹¹ OpenFHE Project. (n.d.). OpenFHE Documentation. ReadTheDocs.

¹² To be consistent with the technical literature, each relevant entity is here referred to as a ‘node’, but it should not be confused with the general use of the word ‘node’ in this report (see also Section 2.2).

Figure 7 An example of the communication in a node-centric workflow. In the first step, the AI vendor sends a query for the interface to the AI-EFFECT platform, which passes it on to the node. The node returns the interface to the AI vendor through the platform, and the vendor implements their AI solution, e.g., in a docker container. The vendor submits the implementation of the AI solution to the platform, which passes it to the node. The node performs the requested tests by interacting with the container and returns the results to the vendor through the platform. The platform may receive the results in a raw format and process or visualize it in a relevant manner.

dataset approval and release, experiment execution, and results publication. Access decisions and privileged operations shall be auditable, enabling traceability of “who did what, when, and under which authorisation context.”

Hardening & Isolation: Hardening and isolation are foundational to security by design, especially when the computation node operates in a cloud environment shared across trust boundaries. The objective is to strictly limit blast radius, prevent lateral movement, reduce attack surface, and ensure that even if one control fails, layered defenses continue to protect data, models, and execution integrity. At the compute layer, all virtual machines or nodes must be hardened using minimal operating system images that include only the components strictly required to run workloads. Security baselines aligned with industry standards should be applied, including disabling password-based access, removing unused services, and enforcing host-level firewalls. Administrative access should be rare, audited, and preferably eliminated in favor of immutable infrastructure and automated remediation.

When confidential computing or trusted execution environments are used, additional isolation measures are required. Secure training and inference workloads must run entirely within confidential virtual machines or enclaves, with cryptographic attestation used to prove the integrity of the runtime environment before sensitive keys or data are released. Debugging interfaces, profiling tools, and memory inspection capabilities must be disabled to prevent leakage.

The trusted computing base inside the enclave must be kept as small as possible by using minimal images and limiting dependencies. Intermediate data and model artifacts should be stored using sealed storage mechanisms that bind access to the enclave identity. These controls collectively ensure that even cloud administrators or compromised hypervisors cannot access data or model material.

Network security: The platform and nodes shall implement network security controls that assume untrusted networks and potential multi-tenancy. Segmentation shall be applied to isolate experiments and tenants, ensuring that workloads cannot communicate laterally unless explicitly permitted by policy. Ingress and egress shall be controlled through explicit allow rules, which is particularly important to reduce exfiltration risks from experimentation workloads and to restrict access to internal services and data stores. Service-to-service communication shall be secured using authenticated and encrypted channels, with strong identity binding between services to prevent impersonation and man-in-the-middle attacks. Network policies should be enforceable at runtime and aligned with the execution workflow, such that only the necessary paths for orchestration, data access, and result reporting are permitted.

Figure 8 Overview of the AI-EFFECT platform and infrastructure security. The word 'node' in this figure should not be confused with the general use of the word 'node' in this report (see also Section 2.2).

Vulnerability management: The platform and nodes shall implement vulnerability management as a continuous operational process rather than a one-time setup activity. Hosts and base images shall be hardened according to established benchmarks, and patching procedures shall be defined to ensure timely updates of operating systems, runtimes, and critical dependencies. Vendor-supplied containers and platform images shall be subject to vulnerability scanning before execution, including scanning of operating system packages and application dependencies, and results shall feed into admission policies that prevent execution of known-critical vulnerabilities without explicit exception handling. In addition, the platform shall maintain an inventory of software components and versions to support impact analysis and rapid response when new vulnerabilities are disclosed.

3.4.4 Overview of options for sharing data and AI solutions

As described in the previous subsections, the interaction between the AI vendor, the node containing the test and experimentation facility, and the AI-EFFECT platform is determined by three main factors:

- Can the involved data be shared?
- Can the AI solution be shared?
- Does the test/experimentation involve physical facilities?

The answers to these three questions determine where the test can be carried out: At the vendor's premise or at the node (or one of its satellites). The data may contain sensitive data and must either be preprocessed before sharing with the vendor or not be shared at all. Conversely, as AI solutions represent intellectual property that is core to the vendors' business cases, it must in many cases also remain confidential. Finally, if the test or experimentation involves a physical test facilities, e.g., as the district heating facilities at SysLab at DTU Wind (see also Section 2), it may not be possible to execute the test at the AI vendor's premise.

In Section 4.1-4.3, we treat each case individually and provide several recommendations on how to use the technologies described in Section 3 to facilitate the interaction between the AI vendor and the node carrying out the test under the assumption that it doesn't involve a physical test facility. In Section 4.4, we provide recommendations for tests that do involve physical facilities.

3.4.5 Data cannot be shared

In this case, we assume that data cannot be shared, but the AI solution may be shared (e.g., because it comes from an open-source repository) and that tests and experimentation can be performed anywhere.

Option 1. If possible, remove the sensitive aspects of the data by anonymizing/pseudonymizing or aggregating it. Alternatively, encrypt the data and perform actions (e.g., training of a neural network)

under the encryption. Finally, it may be possible to synthesize data, e.g., by identifying a statistical model with the same statistical properties as the original data.

Option 2. Perform the test or experimentation at the node.

Option 3. Execute the test in a trusted execution environment (TEE).

It is convenient to perform the test at the AI vendor's premise as in Option 1 because it limits the amount of interaction with the AI-EFFECT platform and the node as well as the corresponding overhead (time, memory, etc.). However, for comparisons or benchmarks of computation time (which is highly relevant to solutions that must be executed in real-time), it is desirable that the solutions are executed using the same hardware and software environments. This can be done at the node (as in Option 2) or in a trusted execution environment (TEE, see also Section 4.5), e.g., if the data comes from a third-party (e.g., a utility company) and cannot be shared directly with the node either.

3.4.6 AI solution cannot be shared

In this case, we assume that the AI solution cannot be shared but the data can be shared freely. Furthermore, the tests can be performed anywhere.

Option 1. Perform the test or experimentation at the AI vendor's premise.

Option 1a. Train the AI solution based on data at the AI vendor's premise but perform the test and experimentation at the node.

Option 2. Encrypt the AI solution and perform the test under the encryption at the node.

Option 3. See Option 3 in Section 3.4.5.

In this case, it is straightforward to perform the tests at the AI vendor's premise. In some cases, the model architecture and the trained weights can be shared for testing purposes, while the training process itself, including methodology and hyperparameters, remains confidential. In such cases, the tests may still be carried out at the node (Option 1a). As discussed in Section 4.1, it may be desirable to carry out the tests with the same software and hardware as other AI vendors, i.e., at the node. In this case, the AI solution may be encrypted and tested while still encrypted (Option 2). Finally, as in Section 4.1, it is also an option to perform the tests in a trusted execution environment (TEE) (Option 3).

3.4.7 Neither data nor AI solution can be shared

Even if both data and the AI solution cannot be shared (and the tests do not involve physical facilities), it is still possible to utilize some of the above approaches.

Option 1. See Option 1 in Section 3.4.5.

Option 2. See Option 2 in Section 3.4.6.

As mentioned earlier, it is desirable to perform the tests at the AI vendor's premises (Option 1). However, it may also be relevant to perform the tests in the same type of environment as other AI vendors, in which case the AI solution can be encrypted (Option 2).

3.4.8 Discussion: Trustworthiness

Testing AI solutions at the AI vendor's premises is convenient and straightforward, but it requires trust that the vendor will conduct the tests properly. If the tests are instead carried out at the node, an independent body controls the environment and tools, making it much more difficult for the vendor to influence or manipulate the results. This increases transparency and strengthens trust in the results. In conclusion, experimentation may be carried out at the vendor's premises in order to refine the AI solution, but if the test results need to be used to convince potential customers or regulatory bodies, it may be preferable to carry them out in a controlled environment at the node where the execution of the test and the interpretation of the results is most credible.

3.5 Tests and experimentation involving physical facilities

Special care is required when workflows involve physical test facilities (e.g., the SysLab facilities described in Section 2.2.1) because they involve operational and administrative constraints, e.g., related to how often an AI solution can be executed or when the test can be carried out^{13,14,15}. In this section, we discuss the following aspects

- Communication between AI vendor and test facility personnel
 - Planning/scheduling of the tests
 - Customization of the test
- Interaction between AI solution and test facility
- Sharing of data and AI solutions

3.5.1 Communication between AI vendor and test facility

Before the experiment. There are multiple reasons why a workflow involving a physical test facility might require direct communication between the AI vendor and the test facility: 1) The test might require scheduling, i.e., the facility must know in advance when to test the solution. If possible, the AI-EFFECT platform may feature an automatic booking functionality if the underlying test facility has such functionality. 2) The test might require customization, e.g., because the test equipment or the involved software may have to be reconfigured for the specific test. For instance, SysLab features the possibility of emulating heat consumers that can either be placed in sequence or in parallel depending on the test objective. 3) It may be necessary to complete a pre-test screening of the AI solution in order to prevent adverse effects on the testing equipment. Such a screening could involve a simulated test run based on a virtual representation of the test, e.g., a simulation based on a mathematical model. 4) The test personnel may inform the vendor about specific details about the test equipment that are relevant to the AI solution, e.g., operational constraints or known special behavior.

During the experiment. It may be necessary or relevant for the AI vendor to be in contact with the test facility personnel to monitor the performance of the AI solution in order to either discontinue the test early if the performance is not satisfactory or if the AI solution is showing undesired behavior.

After the experiment. Depending on the test, it may be relevant for the AI vendor to discuss the experimental results directly with the personnel in order to assess sources of uncertainty, discuss specific reasons for obtaining the specific test results, e.g., details related to the equipment, and to receive concrete suggestions on how to improve the test results.

3.5.2 Interaction between AI solution and test facility

For AI solutions that will interact with the physical test equipment, e.g., by determining appropriate actions in real time based on data, it is necessary to communicate relevant operational constraints in addition to the interface specification. Such constraints may specify how often measurements are obtained and with what time delay (latency), how often the AI solution may take an action, what are the bounds on the actions that may be taken, should the actions be 'close' to previous actions, what is the delay before the action is effectuated (e.g., every 5 minutes), and what data may the action be based on. As mentioned in the previous subsection, it may be necessary to perform a screening of the AI solution in order to verify that executing it with the physical test equipment will not lead to adverse effects.

¹³ <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/12/14/2722>

¹⁴ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-42274-5_2

¹⁵ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8405401>

Figure 9 Example of an internodal sector coupling test case where an AI solution will control a heat pump in order to supply heat to a district heating grid (Danish node) while also providing grid services (German or Dutch node), e.g., to prevent congestions in transmission or distribution grids.

3.5.3 Sharing of data and AI solutions involving physical tests

Depending on the type of data and AI solution (see also Section 2.3), it may be desirable to execute the AI solution at the node when the test or experimentation involves a physical facility. However, if the AI vendor only needs to request batches of training and test (and possibly, validation) data sets, it is also possible to perform the test at the vendor's premise. In contrast, if data is streamed (e.g., if a time series is provided in real-time) and the AI solution must be executed every time a new data point becomes available, it requires significant overhead to execute it at the AI vendor's premise. Consequently, it may be desirable to use one of the approaches described in Section 3.4.6 if the AI solution cannot be shared. More specifically, if the AI solution also provides actions in real-time (e.g., a control algorithm), it is necessary to execute it whenever new data becomes available.

3.6 Internodal testing

The description of the architecture in the previous parts of this section focused on *intranodal* testing, i.e., workflows that only involve a single node. However, a key objective of the AI-EFFECT TEF is to facilitate *internodal* testing as well because many problems in today's energy system can be addressed by sector coupling, i.e., by integrating different energy sectors. In this section, we will describe the special considerations that must be made for workflows involving two or more nodes. In order to make the discussion concrete, we will use another example from the Danish node combined with either the Dutch or German node, which is described in Section 3.6.1.

3.6.1 Example of internodal test

AI solution. In this section, we present an example of an AI solution and a test workflow that would involve two nodes. The objective of the AI solution is to determine whether to use biomass or electricity-powered heat pumps to heat water for a district heating grid. The decision may depend on the electricity prices which vary in time, i.e., the decision must be made on, e.g., an hourly basis. Simultaneously, the objective may be to help prevent congestion in a power grid (transmission or distribution). Consequently, for the sake of the example, we say that it is not possible to perform the test in the Danish node alone¹⁶. Therefore, it is necessary to involve other nodes (e.g., the Dutch or German node) in order to assess the

¹⁶ Note that the Technical University of Denmark which hosts the Danish node also features PowerLab (powerlab.dk) which may support tests related to power grids.

Figure 10 Sketch of the interactions and communication directions in the sector coupling example described in Section 3.7.1 and illustrated in Figure 9.

impact of the AI solution’s operation of the heat pump on the congestion of a given transmission or distribution grid.

Communication. The algorithm will be executed at regular time intervals in order to update the optimal strategy which may depend on both current and future energy prices, i.e., it has to be executed in real time. Consequently, the AI solution will receive temperature measurements from the consumers in the district heating grid (or from critical points in the grid) and communicate operating points for the biomass-fired heating plant and the heat pump. These are all interactions with the Danish node. Additionally, the Danish node will communicate the heat pump power consumption to the power grid, which in turn communicates electricity prices or grid requirements to the AI solution which takes them into account when determining the schedules. All of the communication will happen in real time and requires orchestration between the nodes and the AI solution.

More information. The interested reader may find more information on sector coupling cases like the one described here on the ERIGID 2.0 project page¹⁷ or the technical paper by Silano et al.¹⁸

3.6.2 Orchestrator

As demonstrated in the sector coupling example, executing workflows that involve multiple nodes may require significant efforts in terms of orchestrating communication. Furthermore, some of the recommendations made in the previous section may not apply to workflows involving multiple nodes. For instance, if an AI solution can be shared, but the workflow involves data that cannot be shared outside of the node, the recommendation was to perform the test inside the node. That is not possible if the workflow involves multiple nodes.

Therefore, the AI-EFFECT platform will utilize an orchestrator to be developed in Task 3.1 of WP3. The orchestration will presume that the involved nodes have designed their workflows in the AIoD platform and that they are validated at design time. The orchestrator will coordinate the execution of the individual services in the workflow, determine dependencies, and pass data references.

Deployment and orchestration. As mentioned previously, the workflows may either be executed directly through the AIoD platform or deployed locally at the node, e.g., if it requires significant computational

¹⁷ <https://erigrd2.eu>

¹⁸ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10668976>

resources. If a workflow involving multiple nodes is deployed locally, the nodes should decide beforehand where the orchestrator is located: At either of the nodes or in a cloud-based environment. This will also depend on the privacy considerations discussed in the previous section.

Communication. Conceptually, there are not many differences between workflows involving a single or multiple nodes. However, in practice, the communication between the nodes may require careful consideration and advanced software tools. Therefore, we describe relevant tools such as VILLASnode and functional mockup units and interfaces (FMUs and FMIs) in Section 5.

Special case. In some cases, the additional nodes will only provide data that can be shared with the other nodes, i.e., they essentially constitute data providers, and the workflow can be executed as if it only involved a single node.

3.7 Performance requirements

In Section 4 and 5, we discuss concrete technologies that are relevant to the infrastructure and security layers of the proposed architecture. Based on the described technical requirements, the performance requirements for the implementation and/or deployment of the proposed architecture are consistent with the capabilities of conventional modern commercial servers. Therefore, it is our assessment that the existing nodes as well as new nodes joining the AI-EFFECT TEF would be able to satisfy the performance requirements through commonplace server technology, if they wish to deploy the platform locally. However, the number of required servers will depend on the desired number of simultaneous vendors testing their solutions, which may also be limited by the availability of involved physical test facilities.

4 Technologies and software (information security)

In this section, we describe a range of technologies that are relevant to the security layer of the proposed architecture. The main focus is on technologies that can allow either sensitive data or sensitive AI solutions to be shared with potentially untrusted parties without compromising the details of either. For each technology, we provide a description, relevant references to the open literature, an assessment of the maturity of the technology relative to the timeline of the AI-EFFECT project, challenges and opportunities, and specific technical requirements.

4.1 Synthetization

Description. Data synthetization aims to provide a set of tools that are able to generate synthetic data while being realistic and insightful to real systems. In the era of AI, data is the most crucial element. Yet, in many real-world systems, data is limited and scarce due to security risks, privacy concerns, operation difficulties, etc. Data synthetization is thus a potential resolution to this limitation, enabling the further development of AI solutions to real-world systems. On the other hand, data synthetization provides realistic data sources to enable realistic simulations of the real systems, running and verifying traditional solvers, and so on.

In the first phase of development, the Dutch node focuses on data synthetization for the system of electrical power grids, aimed at providing a full workflow to generate synthetic data needed for running power flows on power grids. This workflow includes:

1. Generating electrical power grids topology that mimics the real-world power grids topology in terms of graph topology characteristics, e.g., number of buses, links, degrees of buses, etc.
2. Generating other power system data attributed to buses, including bus types (generators, loads and connections), generation capacities, dispatches and loads; as well as other power system data associated with transmission lines including transmission line capacities, impedances and so on.
3. Running power flow simulations using the generated data to verify the physical feasibility of data synthetization.

The current data synthetization, led by TU Delft, receives supports from the Dutch TSO. The development would undergo verifications using the Dutch TSO grid data. Dutch node aims to provide the tools as an easy-to-use software with detailed documentations and integrations with popular power system software like Grid2OP and pandapower. An open-source project is used to record the development progress. This software shall be refracted and integrated into the AI-EFFECT platform under the guidelines of WP3.

Literature. SynGrid is an existing MATLAB package for creating synthetic grids data, compatible with MATPOWER. Although SynGrid is not being maintained, it provides synthetization guidelines for the development of data synthetization. Meanwhile, *Aksoy et al. [A generative graph model for electrical infrastructure networks](#), 2018.* offered a random graph model-based power grid topology generation, mimicking the topological behaviors of three large-scale real-world power grid systems. On the other hand, *Elyas et al. [Improved Synthetic Power Grid Modeling With Correlated Bus Type Assignments](#) 2017.* provides a system of statistics-based methods for generating other power system data related to the buses and transmission lines.

Maturity. The first phase of the development, namely, the generation of the grid topology, and other bus- and line-related data, would be completed by September 2026. Specifically, data synthetization shall be able to produce synthetic data that mimics the Dutch TSO grid data and usable by Dutch TSO.

Opportunities. With the data synthetization developed, it serves as a convenient source of power grid data for AI-EFFECT without the limited data concern, or privacy and security constraints. Various AI-based power system solutions can benefit from the tool. Dutch node remains responsible for the maintenance of the tool and the methods used would be open-sourced. Real power grid data provided by Dutch TSO would remain secured within the Dutch node under an NDA. AI vendors would be able to generate synthetic data using their own data or using some characteristics of their data, either of which puts their data under no risks of leakage or being reverse engineered. Data synthetization also poses opportunities to other energy sectors in AI-EFFECT for the more customized development of synthetization tools for the specific data, e.g., from heating systems.

Challenges. There are several challenges to the data synthetization:

1. The original data used to generate the synthetic data shall not be able to reverse engineered from the synthetized data. This poses a strict guideline for the development of the tool. While the tool only makes use of the characteristics of original data, these characteristics may be preferred to be secured by the data holders. This poses a challenge for the tool to generate usable data.
2. The physical feasibility of the generated data remains unknown and shall be guaranteed. There yet exists a challenge to compare the original data and synthetized data due to the limited original data access. Thus, it remains challenging to propose ways to compare the usability of the synthetized data and the similarity to the original data.
3. The focus of Dutch node remains in the power systems and the data of interest. The development for other systems remains rather unspecific and requires more effort.

4.2 Aggregation

Description. Data may be associated with either a spatial or temporal dimension/coordinate (or both) and for many AI solutions and applications in the energy sector, the resolution in either or both coordinates can be very high. For instance, in the Danish node, hourly heat demands are provided for 6,000 customers (smart meters) over a period of several years. This leads to two challenges: 1) It may be restrictively time-consuming for AI solutions to process the data (especially for real-time applications) and 2) it may be possible to infer the identity of customers, even if addresses/spatial coordinates are not provided explicitly.

Aggregation can mitigate both issues by organizing the data into representative clusters. The organization can be designed in many different ways. District heating customers can be clustered based on their geographical location, based on their position in the topology of the heating grid (houses that are close together may be supplied by different pipes), based on their heat demand or type (residential, commercial, industrial), or their distance from the heat supply facility (e.g., a central heating plant). The

specific clustering is highly dependent on the intended use of the aggregated data. For instance, it may not be appropriate to aggregate district heating customers based on their heat demand when determining the forward supply velocity (i.e., how fast the hot water will reach the customers). Furthermore, clustering algorithms can roughly be categorized into 1) *operational methods* where the clusters are determined primarily based on domain-specific knowledge and 2) *data-based methods* where the clusters are determined based on specific aspects of the data in question, e.g., using a K-means algorithm.

Literature. There are many resources that describe data-based clustering techniques that can be used as a basis for aggregation of data¹⁹. Furthermore, data-based clustering techniques have been used for a wide variety of energy-related data, including heat loads in district heating grids²⁰.

Maturity. Both operational and data-based clustering approaches have a high level of maturity and can readily be implemented. However, as mentioned above, it is important to account for the intended use of the aggregated data when using operational methods, and it may be necessary to develop ad hoc solutions. It is expected that for many types of data, such ad hoc solutions can be developed within the time frame of the AI-EFFECT project.

Opportunities. Aggregation is highly relevant to high-resolution data on quantities that are cumulative. For instance, it is straightforward to cluster energy demands because the total demand of the cluster is equal to the sum of the individual energy demands. Furthermore, the aggregation type and level can be customized on a case-by-case basis depending on the data and AI solution. For instance, AI-based heat load forecasts can be customized to, e.g., industrial or residential customers, whereas AI solutions that determine the central supply temperature and velocity would benefit from a topology-based clustering.

Depending on the organization of the node, the aggregation would either be carried out by the data provider, the node owner, or another partner providing a data aggregation service. The responsible partner must aggregate the data and make it available to the node. For data that is streamed, it is necessary to periodically update the aggregated data (e.g., on an hourly, daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly basis). Similarly, if there are changes to the AI-EFFECT platform that require an update to data structures, the aggregating partner would have to update the aggregated data sets. For that reason, it may be necessary to store the original data as well.

Challenges. Aggregation is not straightforward for quantities that are not cumulative, e.g., voltages in a power grid. Furthermore, it is necessary to ensure that the level of aggregation sufficiently anonymizes the identity of the customers. For instance, aggregating heat load demands based on physical addresses is problematic if only a few customers live in a specific area. In that case, a cluster may be so small that it is effectively possible to deduce the heat demand of a specific household. Similarly, if the same data is aggregated into multiple different sets (e.g., one based on customer type and one on topology), it is necessary to ensure that customer identities cannot be inferred by cross-referencing the sets.

Prerequisites. None in particular.

4.3 Anonymization and pseudonymization

Description. Typically, a data point is associated with meta data that provides context. For instance, a measurement of hourly heat consumption may contain a meter ID, location (coordinates), address, or similar. As the meta data can be sensitive, it may be *anonymized* by removing it. Alternatively, the data can be *pseudonymized*, which in many cases can be legally applied instead of anonymization. With pseudonymization each collection of data points (e.g., a column in a .csv file) may be associated with an ID that is linked to a separate file containing the meta data. In that case, the data can be shared with respect to data sharing principles by omitting the meta data file.

¹⁹ Bishop, C. M. (2006). *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. Springer.

²⁰ Gianniou, P., Liu, X., Heller, A., Nielsen, P. S., & Rode, C. (2018). Clustering-based analysis for residential district heating data. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 165, 840–850.

Maturity. This approach is readily available, and it is straightforward to implement by the data providers as they are aware of what meta data to delete or which files to omit.

Opportunities. This approach is simple, cheap, and uncomplicated, and if it is not possible (within reason) to infer any of the meta data from the data itself, e.g., by combining it with publicly available data, it is an effective way to process otherwise sensitive data.

Challenges. The main challenge is that it may be possible to infer the meta data by combining the data from other sources or from the data context. For instance, if a data set with a few time series of heat consumption is provided for a sparsely populated area, it might be possible to match the consumption with the consumer, e.g., if the area contains a small, medium, and large household, a commercial building, and an industrial facility. Consequently, it would be necessary to ensure that that is not possible, which may be laborious and time-consuming. Furthermore, for unstructured data, it may be difficult to automate the process of anonymization.

Prerequisites. None in particular.

4.4 Encryption

Description. Encryption-based computation provides the foundation for secure collaboration between data owners and AI vendors on a shared platform. In this setting, data owners wish to protect the confidentiality of their sensitive datasets, while AI vendors aim to safeguard the intellectual property embedded in their machine learning models. Traditional encryption alone is insufficient because it prevents computation on encrypted content. Advanced cryptographic techniques, notably Homomorphic Encryption (HE) and Secure Multiparty Computation (MPC), address this limitation by allowing computation on protected data without exposing either the raw data or the model parameters.

Literature.

- <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3703452>: provides a comprehensive overview of methods ensuring privacy and security in distributed deep learning, covering both distributed training (e.g., federated learning) and distributed inference (e.g., model-as-a-service). It categorizes existing approaches—including secure aggregation, homomorphic encryption, secret sharing, secure multi-party computation, and differential privacy—and compares them in terms of privacy guarantees, efficiency, and practicality.
- <https://eprint.iacr.org/2025/1310>: provides a structured and in-depth review of methods for building and using decision-tree models on encrypted data by means of homomorphic encryption, motivated by growing privacy requirements in domains such as healthcare, finance and cybersecurity.

Maturity. Encryption-based computation has evolved from theoretical prototypes to emerging practical systems for privacy-preserving machine learning. Homomorphic Encryption has reached a level of maturity that allows efficient encrypted inference for many common deep learning models, especially convolutional and fully connected architectures. Frameworks like Microsoft SEAL, PALISADE, and OpenFHE support HE operations with increasing scalability and developer accessibility. While full training under HE remains a research topic due to computational overheads, parameter tuning and hybrid computation have extended its practical reach. MPC, on the other hand, is considered more deployment-ready for multi-party inference and collaborative training on structured or moderately sized datasets. Libraries such as MP-SPDZ and CrypTen now integrate with standard ML frameworks, reducing the barrier to adoption.

Opportunities. The integration of advanced encryption techniques such as HE and MPC provides a powerful foundation for a platform that connects data owners and AI model providers while preserving

mutual confidentiality. For data owners, encryption ensures that sensitive or regulated datasets can be used for analysis or prediction without ever leaving their trust boundary in plaintext form. For model providers, it guarantees that proprietary parameters and architectures remain protected from disclosure during use. A platform that supports both HE and MPC can offer flexible deployment options tailored to security and performance requirements—HE for single-party encrypted computation with strong cryptographic isolation, and MPC for multi-party collaboration where trust is distributed. This dual capability enables secure model evaluation, encrypted data analytics, and even federated-style training workflows under formal privacy guarantees. By providing developer-friendly APIs, automated key management, and transparent performance trade-offs, AI-EFFECT platform can establish a trusted marketplace for privacy-preserving AI services, allowing organizations to exchange value without compromising intellectual property or compliance.

Challenges. Despite significant progress, encryption-based computation faces substantial performance and operational challenges. Homomorphic Encryption remains computationally intensive, with ciphertext expansion, limited precision, and expensive bootstrapping operations that hinder scalability to large, deep models. Designing ML architectures that are HE-friendly—using polynomial activation functions, shallow depths, and careful parameter scaling—remains an area of active optimization. Secure Multiparty Computation, while capable of exact and flexible computation, is limited by communication overhead and synchronization latency between participants, especially in wide-area or heterogeneous network environments. Efficient protocol design, quantization, and parallelization are essential to making MPC feasible at scale. Additionally, integrating both technologies into modern ML frameworks requires careful consideration of usability, cryptographic key management, and accuracy-preserving model transformation.

Technical hardware requirements

Homomorphic encryption based solution does not require any specialized hardware prerequisites. It is intended to build and run on standard general-purpose machines capable of compiling and executing C++ code (the repo targets a C++14 toolchain and provides a Docker-based install option as well). It typically want a multi-core CPU and adequate RAM (sizing depends on the model/dataset you run, e.g., MNIST MLP/CNN examples).

Technical software requirements

Core build/runtime (C/C++)

- C++ compiler with C++14 support
- CMake \geq 3.10
- GMP (GNU Multiple Precision Arithmetic Library)
- OpenMP
- MNIST Reader (dependency for MNIST examples)
- Build is driven by CMake; the README's example uses a SEAL-related CMake option (-DSEAL_THROW_ON_TRANSPARENT_CIPHERTEXT=OFF).

Python tooling (model + code generation)

- HE-SecureNet's workflow includes generating ONNX graphs and running the ONNX parser that emits private C++ training code.
- Python packages listed by the repo (versions as given): numpy 1.26.4, onnx 1.16.2, onnxruntime 1.18.0, scipy 1.14.1, tensorflow 2.19.0, tf2onnx 1.16.1

Other requirements

- Key management & operational security (deployment): in the intended client–server setup, ensure the secret key stays with the data owner/client, and use secure transport/storage for any public/evaluation keys and encrypted datasets. The framework is designed so the client can remain offline after upload.

4.5 Trusted execution environments and privacy-preserving machine learning

Description of technology. TEE-based computation provides a hardware-assisted foundation for secure collaboration between data owners and AI vendors on a shared platform. In this setup, data owners need to protect the confidentiality of their datasets, while AI vendors seek to preserve the intellectual property and parameters of their models. Traditional encryption protects data at rest and in transit but cannot support computation on encrypted content. TEEs address this limitation through confidential computing, a technology that allows data and code to be processed inside hardware-isolated enclaves. These enclaves ensure that sensitive assets remain protected even from privileged system software such as the operating system, hypervisor, or cloud provider.

In the AI-EFFECT platform, TEEs could enable secure model execution by running the AI vendor’s model inside an enclave that receives encrypted input data from the data owner. Once inside the enclave, the data is decrypted and processed securely within the protected memory, after which the result is re-encrypted and sent back to the data owner. Neither the platform operator nor the AI vendor gains visibility into the other’s assets during the process. Security is further reinforced through remote attestation, which allows both parties to verify the authenticity and integrity of the enclave before sharing any sensitive inputs.

This approach offers a pragmatic balance between privacy and performance. Unlike purely cryptographic techniques such as Homomorphic Encryption or Secure Multiparty Computation, TEEs achieve confidentiality through hardware isolation rather than mathematical encryption, allowing near-native computational performance. This makes TEE-based computation particularly attractive for real-time inference, fine-tuning, and other latency-sensitive machine learning tasks that involve proprietary data or models.

Relevant literature and references.

[ACM Computing Surveys \(2024\)](#): provides a comprehensive overview of methods ensuring privacy and security in distributed deep learning, including trusted execution environments, secure aggregation, homomorphic encryption, and differential privacy. It compares these methods across multiple dimensions—privacy strength, computational efficiency, and deployment feasibility, highlighting TEEs as a mature and practical choice for scalable privacy-preserving AI.

[IACR ePrint 2025/1310](#): Presents a structured and in-depth review of privacy-preserving machine learning methods, discussing the role of TEEs in secure model execution. It analyzes emerging hardware technologies such as Intel SGX, AMD SEV-SNP, and NVIDIA Confidential GPUs, outlining how TEEs bridge the gap between strict data confidentiality requirements and high-performance AI workloads in sensitive domains such as healthcare and finance.

Level of maturity. TEE-based machine learning has evolved rapidly from research prototypes into deployable enterprise solutions. Cloud providers such as Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, and AWS now offer confidential computing instances that integrate Intel SGX, AMD SEV-SNP, or ARM TrustZone. The introduction of GPU-based TEEs (notably NVIDIA’s H100 and Blackwell architectures) extends

confidential computing to high-performance AI acceleration, enabling secure training and inference with minimal overhead. These developments make TEE-based solutions particularly suitable for high-throughput or latency-critical workloads where cryptographic methods remain too slow.

Software ecosystems around TEEs have also matured, with frameworks such as Open Enclave SDK, Gramine, and SCONe providing standardized interfaces for enclave management, attestation, and application deployment. This growing support has significantly reduced the complexity of integrating confidential computing into existing ML pipelines. Nonetheless, TEEs rely on hardware trust; their security depends on the manufacturer's implementation and the integrity of attestation services and require continued investment in secure firmware and side-channel resistance.

Opportunities. The integration of TEE-based computation within the AI-EFFECT platform offers a high-performance, flexible, and trustworthy environment for secure collaboration between data owners and AI vendors. For data owners, TEEs ensure that sensitive datasets are processed exclusively inside hardware-protected enclaves, verifiable through remote attestation, ensuring no data leakage to the platform operator or third parties. For AI vendors, TEEs protect proprietary model parameters, architectures, and training logic during deployment or inference, preventing intellectual property exposure even when models are executed on external infrastructure.

This architecture allows the AI-EFFECT platform to support confidential AI workflows such as private inference, secure fine-tuning, and confidential federated analytics. TEEs provide near-native performance, making them especially well-suited to workloads that demand both speed and confidentiality. By combining attestation management, enclave orchestration, and encrypted communication channels, the platform can act as a trusted intermediary that matches data owners with AI vendors while guaranteeing mutual protection. Additionally, TEEs can be integrated with complementary privacy technologies (such as differential privacy, encrypted logging, or verifiable computation) to meet regulatory and audit requirements in sectors like healthcare, finance, and government.

Challenges/limitations. Although TEE-based solutions provide a practical balance between performance and confidentiality, several technical and operational challenges remain. The most significant concern lies in hardware dependency: the security guarantees of TEEs are tied to the correctness of their implementation and firmware. Vulnerabilities such as side-channel, speculative execution, or rollback attacks have been demonstrated against earlier TEE generations, emphasizing the need for continuous firmware updates and secure attestation workflows.

Memory constraints are another key limitation. Earlier Intel SGX versions offered only a small Enclave Page Cache (EPC) of around 128–256 MB, which restricted the deployment of large machine learning models. The newer Intel SGX M2 architecture has substantially increased the available protected memory to several gigabytes, depending on hardware configuration, significantly reducing the performance penalties associated with memory paging. This improvement makes SGX enclaves far more practical for medium-to-large AI workloads. However, when models exceed available enclave memory, performance degradation can still occur due to paging and context-switching overhead. For very large models (such as modern transformer architectures) techniques like model partitioning, quantization, or offloading computations to GPU-based TEEs remain necessary to achieve scalability. From a platform perspective, orchestrating large numbers of TEE workloads presents challenges in scheduling, attestation management, and key distribution, especially when combining enclaves across heterogeneous hardware (Intel, AMD, ARM, NVIDIA). Finally, while TEEs provide strong practical security, they lack the formal mathematical guarantees of fully cryptographic methods like HE or MPC, making them less suitable for threat models that exclude hardware vendors or infrastructure operators from the trust boundary.

Technical hardware requirements.

- Trusted Execution Environment (TEE): Intel SGX (Scalable SGX)
- Use Intel SGX-capable server CPUs that support large EPC reservations (e.g., ~256–512 GB EPC, depending on SKU/platform).
- EPC is reserved system memory (configured via BIOS/firmware) and requires sufficient DDR capacity to back the reservation.
- Some Intel server platforms support up to 512 GB EPC per CPU (and up to 1 TB EPC on 2-socket systems).
- (Compatibility note) Earlier SGX generations commonly had much smaller EPC (e.g., ~128 MB class), so CPU generation/SKU selection matters.
- Attestation-capable platform
- Hardware/firmware must support SGX remote attestation (commonly via DCAP/ECDSA in data-center settings).

Technical software requirements

1) SGX enablement + drivers

Firmware/boot prerequisites (shows up as “software” in many deployment checklists)

- BIOS/UEFI: SGX enabled + EPC/PRMRR sized appropriately (you mentioned 256–512 GB EPC).
- Flexible Launch Control (FLC): commonly required/expected on server platforms (often a BIOS toggle).

OS-level SGX driver

- Linux kernel with in-tree SGX driver (recommended): Intel SGX support is in mainline Linux from 5.11+ (exposes devices like `/dev/sgx/enclave`, `/dev/sgx/provision`).
- Legacy/out-of-tree driver (only if you can't run a modern kernel): packaged “legacy SGX driver” options exist, but are mainly for backward compatibility with older ABIs.

2) SGX platform software (PSW/DCAP runtime) — concrete packages

If you're on Debian/Ubuntu/RHEL/SLES, Intel publishes package repos and the common baseline set looks like:

Core enclave loader/runtime

- `libsgx-enclave-common` (common enclave loader, used by runtimes)
- `libsgx-urts` (SGX user-mode runtime; needed for Intel SGX SDK-produced enclaves)

AESM service (daemon)

- `sgx-aesm-service` (provides the AESM daemon, typically `aesmd`)

Quote / attestation related baseline

- `libsgx-quote-ex` (universal quote API, installed as a “primary” package in common flows)
- `libsgx-dcap-ql` (DCAP Quote Generation Library)

Common dependent packages you'll usually see pulled in automatically

- `libsgx-ae-qe3`, `libsgx-qe3-logic` (Quoting Enclave + logic)
- `libsgx-ae-pce`, `libsgx-pce-logic` (Provisioning Cert Enclave + logic)
- `libsgx-ae-qve` (Quote Verification Enclave package, used in some verification modes)

- libsgx-aesm-ecdsa-plugin, libsgx-aesm-quote-ex-plugin (AESM plugins for ECDSA/universal quoting)
- libsgx-ae-le (Launch Enclave package, in some dependency sets)

Access control required for quoting on some distros

- Add the quoting user/service account to sgx_prv (Intel notes this for enclaves obtaining quotes via DCAP QGL).

3) Attestation software stack (DCAP / ECDSA) — library names + what runs where

On the attester (the SGX machine generating ECDSA quotes)

- Quote generation API: libsgx-dcap-ql
- AESM daemon + ECDSA/universal quote plugins:
 - sgx-aesm-service
 - libsgx-aesm-ecdsa-plugin
 - libsgx-aesm-quote-ex-plugin
- Quote provider / collateral fetch (PCS or PCCS): libsgx-dcap-default-qpl
- Configure via /etc/sgx_default_qcnl.conf to point at Intel PCS or your PCCS.

On the verifier (service verifying ECDSA quotes) (data owner or ML model owner)

- Quote verification library: libsgx-dcap-quote-verify

4) Enclave build/runtime tooling (how you actually run code in SGX)

- Open Enclave SDK (host/enclave split, with OE APIs; typically paired with DCAP for attestation flows on SGX). <https://github.com/openenclave/openenclave>

5 Technologies and software (infrastructural)

This section describes technologies that are relevant to the infrastructure layer of the proposed architecture, and it focuses on technologies that facilitate sharing of data and AI solutions in a standardized way. As in Section 4, we provide a description, relevant references, a maturity assessment, a discussion of opportunities and challenges, and a list of technical requirements.

5.1 Functional Mock-up Interfaces and Units

Description. Modern engineering systems often require simulations that span multiple domains and tools. A vehicle, for example, might have mechanical, electrical, and software components each best modelled in different simulation environments. Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI)²¹ has emerged as a standard to address this challenge. FMI is a free and open standard that defines how dynamic models can be packaged and exchanged across simulation tools. It allows different modelling tools to interoperate by providing a common interface for model integration. In practice, tools that implement FMI can export their models as standalone Functional Mock-up Units (FMUs)²², which other tools can then import and simulate as part of a larger system.

An FMU is essentially a self-contained model adhering to the FMI standard. Technically, an FMU is distributed as a single zip archive (with the extension “.fmu”) containing everything needed to run a

²¹ The official FMI site provides the specifications, FAQs, and a list of supporting tools. It’s the go-to reference for details on FMI 2.0, 3.0 and the latest developments in the standard. <https://fmi-standard.org>

²² A packaged simulation model that complies with the FMI standard.

model. Inside an FMU, one finds an XML file (called `modelDescription.xml`) that describes the model's interface (its variables, parameters, etc.), along with the compiled code or binaries implementing the model equations, and any additional resources (such as tables, parameter data, or documentation) required for simulation, or understanding. This self-contained packaging means an FMU can be shared and executed on different platforms more easily.

FMI supports different simulation modes for FMUs. In Model Exchange mode, the FMU contains the model equations but relies on the importing tool to provide a numerical solver for integration. In **Co-Simulation** mode, the FMU is truly a “black box” that not only contains the model equations but also includes its own solver algorithm. Both modes use the same FMI packaging, but an FMU for Co-Simulation exposes a do-step function allowing synchronization of multiple models. FMI 2.0 (the most widely used version) introduced robust support for both model exchange and co-simulation, while the newer FMI 3.0 adds features like improved co-simulation coordination, events, and array data handling. For this section we will particularly emphasize co-simulation, since combining multiple FMUs in a joint simulation is a powerful way to build system-level models.

Co-Simulation. Co-simulation is the process of coupling multiple FMUs such that they run together and exchange data to simulate a complete system. Each FMU in co-simulation might have its own internal solver and advances through time independently, pausing at agreed-upon communication points to exchange inputs and outputs with other components.

It's worth noting that co-simulation is not limited to FMUs; one can co-simulate full simulation tools as well; but FMI provides a standard interface for co-simulation, making it much easier to assemble heterogeneous components. By using FMI-compliant units, a wide range of tools (from big commercial simulators to custom Python code) can participate in a joint simulation.

Creating FMUs. One of the strengths of the FMI ecosystem is the variety of ways you can create an FMU. If you are developing a model from scratch, you could implement the FMI interface directly in code (C/C++ or other languages) using the standard header files; essentially “wrapping” your model in the required functions and then compiling it into an executable. There are SDKs and libraries, such as FMI Library (for C) or fmipp/FMI++ (C++), that provide helper code so you don't have to write all the FMI boilerplate yourself. However, in most cases you don't need to program against the FMI API directly: many modelling environments can export FMUs automatically.

Another approach, and the focus of this guide, is creating FMUs from machine learning models or other code using a specialized wrapper tool. We will now look at how to create an FMU by wrapping an existing machine learning model using DNV's MLFMU tool²³.

MLFMU. Machine learning (ML) can be utilized in various ways; for instance, a neural network may act as a surrogate for a complex physical process, or a forecasting model could be employed to predict power grid behaviour. DNV's open-source MLFMU tool is designed to take a trained ML model and package it as an FMU, allowing it to be integrated into any FMI-compliant simulation environment. This capability is particularly valuable in the context of the AI-Effect project, where we might develop AI/ML components and subsequently need to integrate them with physics-based models for co-simulation.

MLFMU expects the machine learning model to be provided in the ONNX²⁴ format, which is a standard format for representing trained neural network models that many frameworks support. In other words, you train your model using TensorFlow, PyTorch, Scikit-learn, or any ML library, and then export or convert that model to an `.onnx`` file. ONNX serves as a common model format, and MLFMU will ingest this and produce a corresponding `.fmu`` file.

Prerequisites. A Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU) is a standardized simulation component that bundles a model and its execution code in a portable package. FMUs conform to the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) standard, which defines a C-based API and metadata that allow the FMU to interact with external

²³ The source code and documentation for MLFMU are available on GitHub. This includes a user guide, advanced usage notes, and examples. <https://github.com/dnv-opensource/mlfmu>

²⁴ Open Neural Network Exchange format for ML models

tools through a well-specified interface. Because the FMU abstracts its internals behind this interface, it can be treated as a “black box,” making it possible to combine heterogeneous components into larger systems and run them in interoperable simulation environments.

The FMI specification defines the C API and the .fmu packaging format. As long as a language can call C functions, it can support FMI; practical implementations exist in C/C++, Java, Python, Rust, Matlab/Simulink, and others.

For co-simulation, FMUs contain their own internal solver and advance their state in response to time-step requests from a master algorithm. To execute such scenarios, a co-simulation master handles time-synchronization and data exchange. An example of this infrastructure is libcosim, developed by the Open Simulation Platform (OSP) initiative. The project also provides a cross-platform CLI tool named cosim, which can run co-simulations, inspect FMUs, and perform testing without a graphical environment.

5.2 VILLASnode

Description. The AI-EFFECT platform is designed in a distributed way. This introduces some challenges. First, it makes it difficult to control and secure data exchanges. Secondly, the gateway between the distributed nodes and their parts needs to be reusable without introducing extra overhead in implementation but saving time and avoiding errors, and it is ideal if it can run in a variety of hardware platforms.

VILLASnode can address the challenges of the distributed platforms. It is an open-source software tool that provides a variety of communication protocols and interfaces to exchange data. It serves as a gateway between different nodes, translates between their protocols streamlining communication between heterogeneous sources, reads from or writes to data bases, and thus facilitates data exchange within and between nodes. It also provides data processing capabilities and because of the modular approach, the diverse individual solutions it comprises can be used as part of a pipeline to achieve any specific desirable result. Especially for node-centric scenarios where all steps are run and coordinated in the platform, VILLASnode is useful as it provides a way to exchange information not only of stored data but also for data streams that work in real-time. For instance, every part of a TEF node runs an instance of VILLASnode with a configuration which specifies the input and output data, their data format, and other processing requirements. Moreover, VILLASnode is available as container which makes it available for different environments and technological platforms, e.g., VMs, servers, Raspberry PIs, and increases the reusability of the platform.

Literature. There are some publications available that show the different use cases supported by VILLASnode:

[A Global Real-Time Superlab: Enabling High Penetration of Power Electronics in the Electric Grid | IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore](#)

[Journal of Open Source Software: VILLASnode: An Open-Source Real-time Multi-protocol Gateway](#)

[Improvements to the Co-simulation Interface for Geographically Distributed Real-time Simulation | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore](#)

[Remote Real-Time Testing of Physical Components Using Communication Setup Automation | IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore](#)

Maturity. VILLASnode has been developed for seven years as open-source project. The development and maintenance are ongoing based on several projects and use cases. Integration and unit tests make sure that existing and new code fulfill code guidelines. Code review is shared between different developers. VILLASnode is already used in a variety of projects. VILLASnode is able to benefit the AI-EFFECT platform directly in case of already supported use cases. Otherwise, adaptations are possible to support the variety of AI-EFFECT services.

Opportunities. VILLASnode introduces the opportunity to couple different TEF nodes and their parts, with an open and free software that implements a variety of standard protocols and data formats, including some from the energy domain. It has the advantage that existing implementations can be reused

without much effort and adapted to the needs of the user. Most of the adaptations are done using a configuration file. Because of its modular structure, new features that require changes in the code can just be added without the additional burden of refactoring other parts of the codebase.

Challenges. VILLASnode might need adaptations to specific AI testing requirements. This might include implementing new data formats or new protocols. Furthermore, the optimal use of VILLASnode needs to be determined for the use cases which defines then how the architecture is designed. The implementation of the code is designed to be lightweight and fast, so the user needs to provide security layers needed, in case it is required by the nature of the highly confidential information or regulations that may apply to the data handled.

Requirements. VILLASnode is an open-source multi-protocol gateway written in C/C++ and available as installation from source and as container which makes it available for different environments and technological platforms, e.g., VMs, servers, Raspberry PIs. The container size is around 2 GB whereas a simple installation from source is around 140 MB.

5.3 Semantic Interoperability

Semantic Interoperability refers to the ability of different systems to exchange data with shared, unambiguous meaning. It goes beyond simple data exchange – ensuring that information is interpreted consistently across platforms, applications, and domains. To achieve this, original data often needs to be transformed into a semantic format (usually a graph-based format like RDF), where concepts and relationships are explicitly defined using ontologies or vocabularies.

The choice of framework depends on the use case:

- When advanced reasoning and inference are required – for example, to derive new insights or support intelligent decision-making, a comprehensive semantic framework like InterConnect SIF (Semantic Interoperability Framework) is appropriate.
- In cases where the goal is primarily to avoid ambiguity and ensure consistent understanding of terms without heavy reasoning, a lightweight model such as SEMAPTIC can be used.

5.3.1 SIF – InterConnect semantic interoperability framework

Introduction and Overview. The Semantic Interoperability Framework (SIF) is the core innovation of the EU-funded Horizon 2020 InterConnect project (2019–2024), which involved 50 partners across 11 countries. SIF enables semantic interoperability among heterogeneous digital platforms, services, devices, and systems in the energy and IoT domains, including smart homes, buildings, and grids. It facilitates unambiguous data exchange and knowledge-based interactions without a centralized authority, thereby addressing critical challenges like data silos, vendor lock-in, and privacy concerns.

Unlike traditional syntactic approaches (e.g., standard APIs), SIF operates at the semantic level by using ontologies to interpret the meaning of data. This enables advanced capabilities such as automated reasoning, dynamic service discovery, and cross-domain integration. The framework pioneers a decentralized model for interoperability, validated in seven large-scale pilots across Europe (in Portugal, Belgium, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Greece, and France) with over 60 integrated systems. SIF supports key use cases like energy efficiency, demand-side flexibility, and applications such as the Common European Reference Framework (CERF) for consumer energy-saving apps.

Key Components. SIF comprises a suite of open-source tools that form a modular and decentralized architecture:

- Semantic Interoperability Layer (Knowledge Engine – KE): The core orchestration engine (developed by TNO) is ontology-agnostic (supporting RDF/OWL) and handles discovery, translation, and reasoning. It includes Smart Connectors for capability registration and knowledge interactions (Ask/Answer and Post/React).

- **Service Store:** A web frontend for ecosystem management (developed by INESC TEC), enabling service registration, browsing, identity provision, service subscription, and data visualization (via the Knowledge Explorer).
- **Generic Adapter (GA):** Provides a unified REST API for secure authentication, authorization, and interaction with the Knowledge Engine (developed by INESC TEC and VIZLORE).
- **Service-Specific Adapter (SSA):** Handles the custom mapping of proprietary data models to the ontologies via graph patterns.
- **Supporting Tools:** Includes an SSA Test Tool, Graph Pattern Visualizer, and compliance testers.
- All components are publicly available on GitHub/GitLab.

Data Transformation. Data transformation is a critical process handled by the Service-Specific Adapter (SSA), which translates proprietary data from a service producer into a semantic format that the Knowledge Engine can understand. This process involves mapping the original data to a manually defined Graph Pattern, which uses classes and properties from standard ontologies like SAREF. By binding the data into this RDF-based format, the SSA ensures it is expressed using shared, unambiguous concepts. The Knowledge Engine then orchestrates secure data exchanges between participants using the ASK/ANSWER and POST/REACT mechanisms. Upon receipt, the consumer's SSA performs the reverse transformation, converting the standardized semantic data (the binding sets) back into a suitable format for its local legacy system, thereby completing the end-to-end semantic loop.

Reasoning Mechanisms. Reasoning occurs within the Knowledge Engine using semantic web technologies. An inference engine applies logical rules defined by the underlying ontologies (RDFS, OWL) to derive implicit knowledge and validate data consistency. For instance, if a service is registered with a specific subclass, the reasoner can automatically infer that it also fulfills queries for its superclass. This capability is fundamental to SIF's automated discovery, allowing the KE to match requests with providers even when their terminology differs syntactically but is semantically related. This automated inference enables robust, dynamic service orchestration and cross-domain functionality without the need for hard-coded integrations.

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Conclusion and Impact. The Semantic Interoperability Framework (SIF) represents a significant advancement toward creating truly integrated and intelligent digital ecosystems for smart energy and IoT. By pioneering a decentralized, ontology-agnostic approach, SIF successfully breaks down data silos, mitigates vendor lock-in, and empowers secure, peer-to-peer data exchange. Its validation across seven large-scale European pilots demonstrates its practical capability to support complex applications like demand-side flexibility and consumer energy services. As an open-source solution with a robust semantic foundation, SIF establishes itself as a critical enabler for the future of European data spaces, providing a vital technological blueprint to foster innovation and accelerate the energy transition. The Semantic Interoperability Framework (SIF) represents a significant advancement toward creating truly integrated and intelligent digital ecosystems for smart energy and IoT. By pioneering a decentralized, ontology-agnostic approach, SIF successfully breaks down data silos, mitigates vendor lock-in, and empowers secure, peer-to-peer data exchange. Its validation across seven large-scale European pilots demonstrates its practical capability to support complex applications like demand-side flexibility and consumer energy services. As an open-source solution with a robust semantic foundation, SIF establishes itself as a critical enabler for the future of European data spaces, providing a vital technological blueprint to foster innovation and accelerate the energy transition.

5.3.2 SEMAPTIC

Description. SEMAPTIC is an innovative, pragmatic approach designed to achieve semantic interoperability without requiring the transformation of original operational data. It acts as a versatile intermediary model, serving as a bridge between raw, syntactically correct data (e.g., JSON, CSV) and rich, reasoning-ready semantic web formats (e.g., RDF, Turtle). Its core concept is to provide contextual meaning by wrapping a semantic specification – based on selected ontologies – into a dedicated model that is embedded directly within the native data structure. The model is implemented via a simple @semaptic JSON object containing three key sections:

- **@prefixes:** Declares the ontologies or vocabularies used, ensuring a common understanding of the underlying data models.
- **@context:** Defines the explicit mapping of each data parameter to specific classes or properties within the declared ontologies, eliminating ambiguity.
- **@annotations:** Enriches the data with discoverability and provenance metadata using standard vocabularies like DCTERMS and DCAT, providing information on version, quality, and usage guidelines.

This approach decouples semantic enrichment from data production. Operational systems can continue to output data in their native, performant formats while simultaneously being enriched with a semantic overlay, making the data self-describing and ready for accurate interpretation by any consumer.

Literature. The SEMAPTIC model was presented and well received in two conferences: MedPower 2024 Conference in Athens^{25,26} and the AIOTI Workshop on Semantic Interoperability for Digital Twins, in Sophia Antipolis, Nice²⁷.

Maturity. SEMAPTIC is a relatively new but promising model, positioned as a practical solution for semantic interoperability. While it leverages mature data formats, like JSON, and established ontologies, its adoption is still in early stages, with implementations primarily in research and pilot projects like HEU ENPOWER. Its JSON-based structure ensures compatibility with widely used data formats, making it accessible to developers and systems. Its potential for adoption is high due to its pragmatic approach to solving the interoperability problem without requiring a complete restructuring of existing systems.

Opportunities. SEMAPTIC presents significant opportunities for enhancing data exchange ecosystems:

- **Pragmatic FAIR Data Implementation:** It offers a practical pathway to make existing operational data instantly FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), enabling secondary use in research, innovation, and analytics without disrupting primary systems.
- **Foundation for Data Spaces:** It is ideally positioned to become a standard semantic layer for data spaces, facilitating trust and seamless data sharing between unknown parties in federated environments.
- **Reduced Overhead and Cost:** By avoiding the need to transform and store all data in complex semantic formats upfront, it significantly reduces computational overhead, storage costs, and system complexity.
- **Backward Compatibility:** Systems can adopt SEMAPTIC incrementally. Data producers can add the @semaptic overlay without altering their existing data structures, lowering the barrier to entry for achieving semantic interoperability.
- **Bridge Between Communities:** It can act as a neutral ground for mapping between different domain-specific ontologies, fostering interoperability across sectors like healthcare, energy, and manufacturing.

Challenges. Despite its potential, SEMAPTIC faces several challenges. Finding or creating appropriate ontologies for diverse domains can be complex, requiring expertise. The model's reliance on shared vocabularies and metadata standards demands robust governance to maintain consistency and prevent misinterpretation. Scaling SEMAPTIC to support complex, dynamic environments without sacrificing simplicity will be critical.

Prerequisites. SEMAPTIC is a data framework designed to ensure a specific level of semantic interoperability. It is well-suited for the AI-EFFECT TEF as it does not require reasoning or inference on the exchanged data. The model will operate in conjunction with the services that produce or consume data to ensure all exchanged information is semantically structured and understood. Accordingly, there are no additional software or hardware requirements.

²⁵ <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/Report-for-AIOTI-Workshop-on-Semantic-Interoperability-for-Digital-Twins-Final-Draft-AIOTI-Layout-1.pdf>

²⁶ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10915879>

²⁷ <https://www.ercim.eu/events/aioti-workshop-on-semantic-interoperability-for-digital-twins#outline-agenda>

5.4 Protocol buffers (protobuf)

Description. Protocol Buffers is Google's open-source, language-neutral, platform-neutral mechanism for serializing structured data—similar to XML or JSON but smaller, faster, and simpler.

Usage in the AI-EFFECT project (WP3). In the AI-EFFECT orchestrator, ProtoBuf serves as the foundational technology for inter-service communication and data exchange across the modular node architecture. We leverage ProtoBuf through gRPC (Google Remote Procedure Call) to enable efficient, type-safe communication between distributed AI services and pipeline components. The orchestrator implements a dynamic protocol adapter layer that compiles .proto schema definitions at runtime, automatically generating Python stub code for service interfaces. This approach allows different vendors and nodes to define their own service contracts (operations, input/output message structures) in .proto files, which the orchestrator dynamically loads and executes without requiring code regeneration or redeployment. ProtoBuf's compact binary serialization format is particularly crucial for our use case, as we handle real-time streaming data flows between energy analysis nodes, support both batch and streaming RPC operations, and need protocol-agnostic interoperability—all while maintaining the security-by-design and zero-trust architecture principles outlined in Task 2.1. As the only data serialization technology officially supported by the AI4EU platform, ProtoBuf ensures that our orchestrator remains compatible with the broader European AI ecosystem while providing the performance and flexibility needed for cross-node experimentation and testing.

Literature. The main resource for information about protocol buffers is the website <https://protobuf.dev>.

Opportunities. As the only data serialization technology officially supported by the AI4EU platform, ProtoBuf ensures that our orchestrator remains compatible with the broader European AI ecosystem while providing the performance and flexibility needed for cross-node experimentation and testing.

Challenges and mitigations. Scope: ProtoBuf defines service interfaces and message types at design time (Layer 1). At runtime (Layer 2), services communicate through a unified control plane that supports REST^{28,29}, gRPC³⁰, VILLASnode, and other protocols, since partners use different technologies. Compatibility: Services must maintain compatible .proto files; changing field numbers or message types can break workflows. Schema dependency: ProtoBuf messages are binary and require the correct schema at both ends. The orchestrator mitigates this for gRPC-based nodes by compiling .proto files dynamically. Runtime enforcement gap: For non-gRPC services (such as REST), interfaces still rely on .proto definitions for the Designer and catalog, but these cannot be automatically enforced at runtime.

6 Summary

In this report, we describe an architecture for the AI-EFFECT TEF, which allows AI vendors to test their solutions at test and experimentation facilities across Europe. The test facilities (physical or virtual) are organized into nodes, and each node may contain multiple types of stakeholders: The owner, test facility management, data handlers, and data providers. The tests and experiments are organized into workflows that are composed of individual services. The reason is that a given workflow may use the same service as another workflow, e.g., data provision or training of a neural network. The workflows are intended to be implemented at the AIoD platform, and they may either be executed directly at the AIoD platform or deployed locally at the node if more computational resources (memory or computing power) are necessary. Alternatively, the node may also use a cloud solution for executing the workflows, or they may be deployed at the vendor's premises and executed there.

AI-EFFECT platform. The AI-EFFECT TEF will feature a separate platform where AI vendors can browse through use cases, test facilities, and nodes. The platform will serve as a single-point entry for the AI

²⁸ Representational state transfer.

²⁹ Fielding, Roy Thomas, 2000. "Chapter 5: Representational State Transfer (REST)". *Architectural Styles and the Design of Network-based Software Architectures*. PhD thesis. University of California, Irvine, USA.

³⁰ Remote procedure call (RPC) framework. Link: <https://grpc.io>.

vendors to establish contact with the nodes and execute the workflows. The platform should facilitate the communication with the node, e.g., by parsing requests for AI solution interfaces to the nodes and parsing the interfaces back. Similarly, the platform may also parse tests results back if they are executed at the node, and it may also visualize them for the vendor.

Workflows. As mentioned above, the workflows may either be intended to be executed at the node (node-centric) or at the vendor's premises (vendor-centric). The node-centric designs also includes execution at the AIoD platform or using another cloud solution. In the report, we discuss how to handle situations where either the data, the AI solution, or both cannot be shared, e.g., by aggregating the data or encrypting the AI solutions. Furthermore, we discuss how communication internally in the node should be handled, e.g., through identity and access management, security by design, and network security. Finally, we also discuss the implications of workflows involving physical test facilities or involving multiple nodes.

Technologies and software: Information security. As the architectural design is based on an assessment of the technological capabilities, we discuss relevant technologies for sharing data or AI solutions. Specifically, we discuss the challenges, opportunities, and technical requirements of synthetization, aggregation, anonymization/pseudonymization, and encryption of data, encryption of AI solutions, and execution of workflows in a trusted execution environment (TEE).

Technologies and software: Infrastructure. We also discuss technologies that are relevant to the infrastructure layer of the architecture, i.e., for implementing workflows that can be executed at the AIoD platform (protobuf), for communicating and implementing interfaces specified by the workflows (functional mockup units/interfaces), for facilitating real-time communication (VILLASnode), and for sharing data unambiguously (SIF and SEMAPTIC).

